

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE UNITED KINGDOM'S PRACTICE IN MANAGING THE TRAINING SYSTEM OF INDIVIDUAL ATHLETES THROUGH DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Junaydullayev Mels Asliddin ugli

Bukhara State University Department of Sports Activities

Associate Professor (PhD)

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19725786>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 19th April 2026

Accepted: 21st April 2026

Online: 23rd April 2026

KEYWORDS

The practice of using digital educational technologies in managing the training system of individual athletes in the country has a deeply scientific foundation

ABSTRACT

In developed countries around the world, reforms aimed at improving the efficiency of managing the training system of individual athletes through the use of digital educational technologies have been consistently implemented since 2015. As a result, these countries have succeeded in establishing globally leading practices, and studying their experience is of great importance for economic research.

In developed countries around the world, reforms aimed at improving the efficiency of managing the training system of individual athletes through the use of digital educational technologies have been consistently implemented since 2015. As a result, these countries have succeeded in establishing globally leading practices, and studying their experience is of great importance for economic research.

This situation can be explained by the fact that, in developed countries, the use of digital educational technologies in managing the training systems of individual athletes has gained strategic significance in increasing the economic efficiency of system management. Therefore, through an in-depth analysis of leading practices in developed countries regarding the management of individual athlete training systems based on digital educational technologies, identifying the possibilities of applying such experiences in national practice is of both scientific and practical relevance in economic science.

The practice of using digital educational technologies in managing the training system of individual athletes in the country has a deeply scientific foundation. Due to this, the efficiency of system management demonstrates a stable growth trend. At the same time, compared to other countries, it is distinguished by its high capacity to develop forecast parameters for improving management efficiency priorities.

Based on the research conducted by foreign scholars such as S. V. Caro [1], J. Holden [2], and E. Neupert [3], dedicated to the practice of using digital educational technologies in the management of the training system of individual athletes in the United Kingdom, several features specific to the national practice were identified (see Figure 1), and the following conclusions were formed:

Unlike Germany and United States, individual sports schools in the United Kingdom carry out the analysis of athletes' physical, psychological, biomechanical, tactical, and technical data through their own private digital educational platforms, with the participation

of coaching staff and industry specialists. This indicates that digital educational platforms in the country's training system for individual athletes are organized in a decentralized manner.

Fi

Figure 1. Characteristics of the United Kingdom's Practice in Managing the Training System of Individual Athletes through Digital Educational Technologies

In collecting the physical, psychological, biomechanical, tactical, and technical data of individual athletes, the United Kingdom, similarly to Germany, uses sensor-based wearable devices and tracker technologies installed on athletes' clothing and bodies. In addition, athletes are required to complete daily psychological tests.

Based on an in-depth analysis of athletes' data conducted by sports coaches and industry specialists working in schools for training individual athletes, planned educational and sports training programs are developed to optimize athletes' performance through an individual approach. The overall priority of these programs is characterized by achieving high results in international competitions.

The analysis of practices in the United Kingdom, as one of the advanced Western countries in the use of digital educational technologies for managing the training system of individual athletes, has shown that these processes make it possible to achieve the following results in system management:

1. The introduction of digital educational technologies into the management of the training system of individual athletes creates opportunities to ensure a high level of economic and managerial efficiency.
2. Digital educational technologies significantly reduce the costs associated with managing the training system of individual athletes.
3. Digital educational technologies contribute to the development of planned programs consisting of educational and sports training workloads based on an individual approach that corresponds to the athlete's personal abilities, as well as their psychological, physical, biomechanical, tactical, and technical readiness.

Based on our research, it was concluded that the most optimal option for Uzbekistan, through the creative use of the United Kingdom's experience among advanced Western countries in applying digital educational technologies for managing the training system of individual athletes, is to develop a hybrid adaptation program. This program would allow the balanced use of the practices of all three countries.

At the same time, such creative adaptation would require relatively lower investment demand and, in the medium-term perspective—more specifically within the next 3–5 years—is expected to increase the economic efficiency of managing the training system of individual athletes in Uzbekistan through the use of digital educational technologies.

References:

1. Caro C.V., Trow S., Bell Z., Flynn A.C., Lavelle F. The Translation of Policy to Person: A Qualitative Analysis of Elite Athletes' Perceptions of Pregnancy in the United Kingdom. *Sports Medicine*, Vol. 55, 2025. – pp. 1293-1306
2. Holden J., Wagstaff Ch.R.D., Wadey R., and Brown P. Exploring the barriers to athlete personal development within UK Olympic and Paralympic sport. *Psychology of Sport & Exercise*, Vol. 81, 2025. – pp. 1-11. DOI: 10.1016/j.psychsport.2025.102966
3. Neupert E., Gupta L., Holder T., and Jobson S.A. Athlete Monitoring Practices in Elite Sport in the United Kingdom. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, Vol. 40 (8), 2022. – pp. 1-8. DOI: 10.1080/02640414.2022.2085435

